

Management

WORK SATISFACTION AMONG EMPLOYEES AT VIRASAT-E-KHALSA: ANANDPUR SAHIB

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ABSTRACT

Work satisfaction is a general attitude of employees towards one's job. The present study is undertaken to assess the work satisfaction among employees at Virasat-e-Khalsa through percentage and graphic analysis. The sample size of 30 respondents was selected through convenience sampling. It was found that overall satisfaction was moderate, however, salary and job security are a major concern for the youth working there. It was suggested that job satisfaction may be improve by assuring regular appointments and increments in remuneration.

Keywords:

Work Satisfaction, Employees, Virasat -E- Khalsa, Job Satisfaction.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Work or Job satisfaction has been defined as delightful or positive emotional state as a consequence of an appraisal of one's job (Locke, 1969). It refers to how content or satisfied employees are with their work. It is relatively recent term since in previous centuries the work available to a particular person was often predetermined by the occupation of that person's parent. There are a variety of factors that can influence a person's level of work satisfaction. Some of these factors include the level of pay and benefits, the perceived fairness of the promotion system within a company, the quality of the working conditions, leadership and social relationships, the work itself (the variety of tasks involved, the interest and challenge the work generates, and the clarity of the work description/requirements). The happier people are within their work, the more satisfied they are said to be. Work satisfaction is not the same as motivation, although it is clearly linked. Work design aims to enhance work satisfaction and performance methods include work rotation, work enlargement and work enrichment. Other influences on satisfaction include the management style and culture, employee involvement, empowerment and

autonomous workgroups. Work satisfaction is a very important attribute which is frequently measured by organizations. It is essential for the employee retention. The most common way of measurement is the use of rating scales where employees report their reactions to their works. Majority of the workers are concerned more about the salary rather than other factors which are equally responsible for the level of satisfaction, like canteen facilities, rest rooms, perks, working conditions, etc. these conditions are considered less significant when compared to salary.

VIRASAT- E- KHALSA

Virasat-e-Khalsa is a museum of Sikhism, located in the holy town, Anandpur Sahib, near Chandigarh, the capital of the state of Punjab, India. The museum celebrates 500 years of the Sikh history and the 300th anniversary of the birth of Khalsa, based on the scriptures written by the tenth and last guru, Guru Gobind Singh. An internationally acclaimed architect Moshe Safdie, initiated the design process for the Virasat-e-Khalsa. Its architect got an insight from the historic Golden Temple and the rich heritage of Anandpur Sahib — its hills, natural valleys and streams, the Anandgarh Fort and the glorious Gurdwara Keshgarh Sahib. In Moshe Safdie's own words, "a building cannot be experienced as independent of the land in which it is rooted."

RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of the study is to explore overall work satisfaction among the employees of Virasat-e-Khalsa. The study sheds some light on how work satisfaction varies with the age, gender, department, tenure and job role of the employee. The study aims to capture the suggestions on improvement areas that would help to achieve higher satisfaction levels in the future

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee work satisfaction is the feelings and thoughts of employees about their work and place of work. In result, work satisfaction is all about to satisfy the one's needs in working place (Togia et al., 2004). Bodur (2002) stated that there are some factors, which are related to work satisfaction that is work substances, age, sex, educational level, work place environment, location, colleagues, income and timing of work. For the purpose of employee satisfaction many theories have been developed. The most important theory is Maslow's need theory. It is based on human hierarchical needs. On the other hand, job satisfaction relates to significant conventional views, which are formulated via Mausner and Herzberg (1959). Maslow's theory is based on fundamental and external element such as accomplishment, acknowledgment, duty, pay, plan, interpersonal interaction, management, and operational atmosphere. Statt (2004) work satisfaction can be defined also as the extent to which worker is content with the rewards he or she gets out of his or her job, particularly in terms of intrinsic motivation. Spector (1997) refers to job satisfaction in terms of how people feel about their jobs and different aspects of their jobs.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study the work satisfaction of the employees.
- To know the opinion about working environment in the organization.

4. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- Whether the employees are happy with the salary they are fetching?
- What motivates the employees to work more efficiently?
- How likely the employees are to change their job?

5. METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted on a sample of 30 respondents who were selected using Non-probability convenience sampling techniques. The sample includes the employees from Visitors Services Assistance (VSA), Technical staff, Housekeeping and Security Guards (Table no. 1). The primary data was collected via self-made structured closed-ended Questionnaire. The response format was multiple choice questions.

		<i>Number of Employees</i>	<i>Percentage of employees</i>
Gender	Male	19	63%
	Female	11	37%
Religion	Sikh	23	76%
	Non-Sikh	7	24%

6. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The data is analyzed through simple analysis technique. The data tool is percentage method.

$$\text{Percentage of Respondents} = \frac{\text{No. of Respondents}}{\text{Total no of respondents}} \times 100$$

The responses are represented using graphic analysis.

<i>S. no.</i>	<i>Variables</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
1	Pay	61
2	Qualification	64
3	Working Conditions	70
4	Job Security	48
5	Relation with Co workers	70

7. FINDINGS

- 1) Overall work satisfaction level is relatively moderate.
- 2) The factors contributing to satisfaction level were interpersonal relations, working environment, the organization's facilities and the scarcity of human resources.
- 3) Generally, people in Visitors Services Assistance (VSA) are more likely to look for other job as they feel that their present job doesn't justify their qualification and they are being paid less in comparison to their counterparts.
- 4) In respect with the career development, the contractual staffs were dissatisfied. They felt that they had little job security in their present job. Most of the employees were on contractual basis and according to them there is no provision for regular appointments.

8. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- 1) All the findings and observations made in the study are purely based on the respondents answers which may be biased
- 2) A large number of respondents could not be selected for the study because they were engaged with their duties.
- 3) Few respondents did not disclose any information since they felt it was a confidential matter.
- 4) Time constraint.

9. SUGGESTIONS

A stable, secure work environment that includes job security should be provided to the employees. The provision of perks and bonus for motivating the employees to work efficiently and to improve the retention rate in the organization. An extensive study needs to be undertaken in this area.

10. REFERENCES

- [1] Spector, P. E. (1997). *Industrial & organizational psychology (2nd ed.)*. New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- [2] Togia, A., Koustelios, A. and Tsigilis, N. (2004), "Job satisfaction among Greek academic librarians", *Library & Information Science Research*, Vol. 26, pp. 373-83.
- [3] Statt, D. (2004). *The Routledge Dictionary of Business Management, Third edition*, Routledge Publishing, Detroit, p. 78
- [4] Herzberg, F. and Mausner, B. (1959), *The Motivation to Work, 2nd ed.*, Wiley, New York, NY.
- [5] AL-Hussami M (2008). A Study of nurses' job satisfaction: The relationship to organizational commitment, perceived organizational support, transactional leadership, transformational leadership, and level of education. *Eur. J. Sci. Res.*, 22(2): 286-295.
- [6] Arnolds, C.A., & Boshoff, C. (2001). The challenge of motivating top management: A need satisfaction perspective [Electronic version]. *Journal of Industrial Psychology*, 27(1), 39-42.

[7] Griffin MA, Patterson MG, West MA (2001). Job satisfaction and team work: the role of supervisor support. *J. Organ. Behav.*, 22: 537-550.

[8] www.shodhganga.com

[9] www.emraldinsight.com

[10] <http://journals.ama.org/doi/abs/10.1509/jmkr.39.3.336.19105>

APPENDIX

Questionnaire used for collecting primary data

Work Satisfaction among Employees: A Study of Virasat-E-Khalsa

Name: _____ Gender: _____

Age: a) Below 20 b) 20-30 c) 30-40 d) 40-50 e) 50 above

Hometown: _____ Religion: _____

Educational Qualification: _____

Job Profile: _____

Nature of Job: Regular/Contractual/Others

Year of Joining: _____

How challenging is your job?

- A) Extremely Challenging
- B) Very challenging
- C) Moderately Challenging
- D) Slightly Challenging
- E) None

How much salary do you earn?

- A) Below 5000
- B) Between 5000-10000
- C) Between 10000-15000
- D) Between 15000-20000
- E) Above 20000

Are you satisfied with the salary?

- A) Extremely well
- B) Very well
- C) Moderately well
- D) Slightly well
- E) None

Is there any training programme related to your job?

- A) Yes
- B) No
- C) Don't know

Is there any provision of job rotation at your work place?

- A) Yes
- B) No
- C) Don't know

Do you feel that your job justifies your qualification?

- A) Strongly Agree B) Agree
- C) Slightly Disagree D) Disagree E) None

Are you satisfied with the relationship existing with your co-workers?

- A) Yes B) No

Are you satisfied with the working conditions at your work place?

- A) Strongly satisfied B) Satisfied
- C) Strongly dissatisfied D) Dissatisfied E) None

What motivates you to work more efficiently?

- A) Salary B) Promotion C) Less supervision
- D) Good Working Conditions

How likely are you to look for another job?

- A) Extreme likely B) Moderately Likely
- C) Slightly likely D) Likely E) None